

Free Radical Scavenging Activity of Methanol Leaf Extract of *Moringa oleifera*

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ABSTRACT

Moringa oleifera (Horse radish/Drumstick/Miracle Tree) is a medicinal plant with various parts of the plant employed for therapeutic purposes. The study evaluated the antioxidant activity, phytochemical composition, and free radical scavenging activity of the methanol extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaf. The percentage yield of the methanol extract was determined to be 6.5%. Qualitative phytochemical screening detected the presence of flavonoids, phenols, alkaloids, tannins, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinone, and steroids, while saponin was absent. The result of quantitative phytochemical analysis revealed total phenolic content (177.5 ± 3.37 mg GAE/g), flavonoids (49.5 ± 8.99 mg QE/g), tannins (65.3 ± 5.45 mg GAE/g), and alkaloids (81.5 ± 3.84 mg AE/g). Antioxidant activity was assessed using the DPPH radical scavenging method, showing a concentration-dependent increase in inhibition, i.e., activity increases with an increase in concentration, with a maximum of $66.2 \pm 2.32\%$ at $1000 \mu\text{g/ml}$ compared to that of standard antioxidant ascorbic acid at the same concentration, to be $81.9 \pm 0.1\%$. The FRAP assay revealed reducing power comparable to ascorbic acid, with Fe^{2+} equivalents of 2.71 ± 0.01 mM and 2.77 ± 0.01 mM, respectively. The findings suggest that *Moringa oleifera* leaf possesses significant antioxidant potential and valuable phytochemicals, making it a promising source for nutraceuticals for therapeutic applications.

Keywords: Frap Assay; Nutraceuticals; Moringa; Phytochemicals; Scavenging; Inhibition

INTRODUCTION

Free radicals are highly reactive molecules with an unpaired electron in their outer shell, which makes them unstable. They actively participate in redox reactions. The oxidation process in the human body damages cell membranes and other structures, including cellular proteins, lipids, and DNA. Oxygen is metabolized to generate unstable free radicals that steal electrons from other molecules, causing damage to DNA and other cells. The body produces these reactive species, such as the hydroxyl radical (OH) and superoxide radical (O_2^-), through metabolic processes like respiration, immune defense mechanisms, and the cytochrome P450 system. External factors, such as smoking, pollution, and radiation, can also contribute to free radical production (Flieger et al., 2021). The body balances the generation of free radicals with the help of the antioxidant defense system; when this balance shifts in favour of free radicals, oxidative stress occurs, damaging cellular structures and disrupting normal physiological processes linked to aging, cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease (Forman and Zhang, 2021). Oxidative stress may also occur as an increase in the rate of ROS production, deficiencies of low-molecular-weight antioxidants, and inactivation of

enzymes with antioxidant activity. Increased and/or prolonged state of oxidative stress may cause serious damage to the cell and even death (Tiwari et al., 2011). Antioxidants inhibit the oxidation of other molecules by neutralizing free radicals and reducing oxidative stress in the body. They donate electrons to unstable molecules (free radicals), stabilizing them and reducing their harmful effects. Antioxidants play a crucial role in maintaining overall health and preventing various diseases by protecting cells, proteins, and DNA from damage caused by oxidative stress. They can be obtained from foods, including fruits, vegetables, nuts, seeds, and whole grains, and can also be synthesized endogenously by the body (Adwas et al., 2017).

These molecules are produced by the protective system of various organisms to respond to the destructive effects of free radicals. They can reduce the damage caused by ROS/RNS and even chlorine. The action of the protective system may limit the negative effects of free radicals by preventing the formation of reactive radicals or by interrupting free radical reactions (Gulcin, 2020). Plants with high content of compounds with antioxidant properties can capture free radicals (carotenoids, phenolics, flavonoids, anthocyanin derivatives, unsaturated fatty

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acids, vitamins, enzymes, and cofactors) has stimulated interest in using them in defensive and therapeutic natural medicine (Hrelia and Angeloni, 2020).

The human body has an inherent antioxidant defense system, comprising enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase, which work together to neutralize free radicals. However, this defense system can be overwhelmed by various factors, including environmental stress, lifestyle choices, and genetic predispositions, leading to a state of oxidative stress. This is where dietary antioxidants come into play, providing a vital layer of protection against oxidative stress and its associated health consequences (Rahal *et al.*, 2014). Dietary antioxidants come in various forms, including vitamins C and E, beta-carotene, polyphenols, and other phytochemicals. These compounds can be found in a wide range of plant-based foods, such as fruits, vegetables, nuts, and seeds. The antioxidant properties of these compounds have been extensively studied, with research demonstrating their ability to scavenge free radicals, reduce inflammation, and promote overall health (Singh and Kumar, 2017). Antioxidants have numerous health benefits, with evidence suggesting that they can reduce the risk of chronic diseases, such as cancer, cardiovascular disease, and neurodegenerative disorders. They have been shown to improve immune function, reduce the signs of aging, and promote cognitive health. With the global burden of chronic diseases on the rise, the importance of antioxidants in human health cannot be overemphasized (Fitriana *et al.*, 2016).

The Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) test is a typical SET-based method measuring the reduction of the complex of ferric ions (Fe^{3+})-ligand to the intensely blue ferrous complex (Fe^{2+}) through antioxidants in acid environments. Antioxidant activity is determined as an increase in absorbance at 593 nm, and the results are expressed as micromolar equivalents of Fe^{2+} with a standard antioxidant. Unlike other SET-based methods, the FRAP test is carried out in acidic pH conditions (pH = 3.6) to maintain iron solubility. Reaction at low pH decreases the ionization potential that drives electron transfer and increases the redox potential, causing a shift in the dominant reaction mechanism. The original FRAP test uses tripyridyl triazine (TPTZ) as the linking ligand to the iron ion, while alternative ligands were also used to bind the iron ion, such as ferrozine, to assess the reducing power of ascorbic acid (Munteanu and Apetrei, 2022).

Free radicals are constantly generated in the body as a result of metabolic processes such as respiration, immune defense mechanisms, and the cytochrome P450 system. Also external factors like smoking, pollution, and radiation can also contribute to free radical production these radicals can overpower the antioxidant defense system of the body, leading to oxidative stress which affects the lifestyle of individuals and will make individuals prone to many diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease. The Moringa leaf contains almost all essential nutrients, growth factors, vitamins, amino acids, proteins, minerals, and metals like potassium, iron, and zinc. Besides these, nowadays, plant leaves may be used to prepare various nutritional supplements and medicine (Muhammad and Abubakar, 2022).

The aim of this study is to determine the free radical scavenging activity of Methanolic *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract using the DPPH free radical scavenging assay and FRAP assay.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Methanol (99.5% v/v), Quercetin (standard), Gallic acid (standard), Distilled water, NaOH, AlCl_3 , NaNO_3 , Folin's reagent, Na_2CO_3 , DPPH (0.1M), Methanol (50%), Atropine (Standard), Ascorbic acid (Standard), TPTZ (0.01M), HCl (35%), $\text{FeL}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Acetate Buffer, FeSO_4 (Standard). All other reagents used were of analytical grade except where otherwise stated. Fresh samples of *Moringa oleifera* leaf were collected from a garden located in New Millennium City, Kaduna, Kaduna State. The sample was taken to the Dept of Biological Science for authentication and was issued a voucher number (KASU/BSH/774).

Extract Preparation

Extraction was carried out for *M. oleifera* leaves by using maceration techniques. About 10g of the powdered sample was soaked in 100 mL of methanol (99.5%) for 48 hrs. at room temperature. The soaked sample was shaken intermittently during the extraction period and subsequently filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper to obtain the methanolic extract. The extract was concentrated by Timoshnikov *et al.* (2022). to dryness at 40° C and weighed to determine the extraction yield, which was calculated following the method of Mahmoud *et al.* (2017).

Extraction yield (%) = $\frac{\text{Weight of the extract}}{\text{Total weight of the Raw material}} \times 100$

Qualitative Screening of Phytochemicals

Phytochemical examinations were conducted qualitatively according to the method of Timoshnikov *et al.* (2022). The test for flavonoids (alkaline reagent test) involved adding a drop of 10% NaOH to 1 ml of distilled water and the extract. The formation of a yellow colour indicated the presence of a flavonoid compound. The test for saponins (frothing test) required taking a small portion of the extract and dissolving it in distilled water, shaking vigorously for about 3-5 minutes. The formation of a layer of foam (froth) that lasted for several minutes indicated the presence of saponins. The test for cardiac glycosides (Keller-Killian's test) was performed by adding a small portion of the extract into a clean test tube, followed by the addition of 1 ml of glacial acetic acid containing traces of 3.5% ferric chloride solution. 1 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ was carefully poured onto the walls of the tube to form a lower layer. A reddish-brown ring at the interface indicated the presence of glycosides (Timoshnikov *et al.*, 2022). The test for steroids (Salkowski test) involved dissolving a small portion of the extract in 1 mL of chloroform, to which 1 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ was carefully added to form a lower layer. A reddish-brown colour at the interface indicated the presence of a steroidal ring (Nanna *et al.*, 2013). The test for tannins (lead acetate test) was conducted by adding 3 drops of lead acetate to 1 mL of the extract solution. The formation of a creamy gelatinous precipitate indicated the presence of tannins (Sheel *et al.*, 2014).

The test for phenols (ferric chloride test) involved adding 1 ml of extract solution and a few drops of 5% ferric chloride solution. The formation of a dark green colour indicated the presence of phenolic compounds (Timoshnikov *et al.*, 2022). The test for alkaloids (Mayer's test) was carried out by adding a drop of Mayer's reagent to 1 mL of extract solution. The formation of a creamy white precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids (Auwal *et al.*, 2014). The test for anthraquinone (Bontrager's test) was conducted by adding a small portion of the extract into a clean test tube, followed by the addition of chloroform and equal amounts of 10% ammonia. The formation of a pink colour in the upper layer indicated the presence of anthraquinone (Timoshnikov *et al.*, 2022). Determination of total phenolic content (TPC): The estimation of total phenol content was measured using a microplate reader by the Folin-Ciocalteu method, with gallic acid as the standard (Fazia *et al.*, 2022). Aliquots of 0.02 mL of the test sample were added into 3 wells of the microplate, followed by the addition of 0.15 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu, and allowed to stand for 5 minutes. Then, 0.08 mL of sodium carbonate (7.5 w/v) was added to each well, and the solutions were

incubated at room temperature for 60 min. The absorbance was measured at 765 nm (microplate reader) using 0.02 mL of methanol as a blank. All samples were reanalyzed in three replications. Standard preparation involved creating a stock solution of gallic acid 1 mg/mL; aliquots of 0.12, 0.14, 0.16, 0.18, and 0.2 mL were taken and made up to a total volume of 1 mL. The total phenolic content of the plant was then calculated as shown below in the equations and expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE)/g of extract. Analysis was conducted in triplicate, and the mean value was considered. The phenolic content was calculated as follows: $C = c \cdot v / m$, where: C = total content of phenolic compounds in gallic acid equivalent (GAE), c = concentration of gallic acid established from the calibration curve (mg/ml), V = volume of extract (ml), and m = mass of the methanolic extract (g).

Determination of Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)

The TFC of *Moringa oleifera* was determined by aluminium chloride assay (AlCl₃ Colorimetric method) with a little modification (Malikarjuna and Tripathi, 2012; Chatterjee and Goswami, 2012; Munteanu and Apetrei, 2022). A stock solution of quercetin 1 mg/ml was prepared, aliquots of 0.12, 0.14, 0.16, 0.18, and 0.2 mL were taken, and made up to a total volume of 1 mL with 50% methanol. Aliquot of 0.02 mL of the test sample was added to the microplate, and 0.015 mL of sodium nitrite (5% NaNO₂, w/v) solution was added. After 6 minutes, 0.015 mL of (10% ALCL₃, w/v) solution was added. The solution was allowed to stand for 6 minutes, and after that, 0.08 mL of sodium hydroxide (4% NaOH, w/v) solution was added to the mixture and was allowed to stand for another 15 minutes. The total flavonoid content of the plant was then calculated as shown below in equations and expressed as mg quercetin equivalent (QE)/g of extract: $X = q \times V / w$, where X = total content of flavonoid compound in quercetin equivalent, q = concentration of quercetin established from the standard curve, V = volume of extract (mL) m = mass of the methanolic extract (g). Analysis was conducted in triplicate, and the mean value was considered.

Determination of Total Alkaloid Content (TAC)

TAC was quantified by the spectrophotometric method as described by Gulcin (2020) with slight modification. This method is based on the reaction between alkaloids and bromocresol green (BCG). 5 mg of the methanol extract was weighed and dissolved in 2 mL of 2 N HCL (2.5 mg/mL), 0.5ml of the sample was added into a separating funnel, followed by the addition of 2.5 mL of chloroform, then 2.5 mL of BCG and 2.5 mL of phosphate buffer at pH 7. The mixture

was shaken vigorously, chloroform remained denser at the bottom, and then it was drained. The remaining mixture was reacted and was taken into separate test tubes. The absorbance was measured at 470 nm. The whole experiment was conducted in three replicates. The total alkaloid content of the plant was then expressed as mg atropine equivalent (AE) / g of extract.

Determination of Total Tannin Content (TTC)

The total tannin content was determined by the Folin-Ciocalteu method as described by Malakarjuma and Tripathi (2012). 0.5 mL of extract was added into 3 wells of a microplate, followed by the addition of 0.175 mL of distilled water and 0.01 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu phenol reagent, 0.02 mL of 35% Na₂CO₃, and the solution was kept at room temperature for 30 minutes. A set of reference standard solutions of Gallic acid (0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08, and 1 mg/mL) was prepared in the same manner as described earlier. Absorbance for sample and standard solutions was measured against the blank at 725 nm with a microplate reader spectrophotometer. The tannin content was expressed in terms of mg of GAE/g of extract.

Determination of Free Radical Scavenging Activity DPPH(2,2-di(4-tert-octylphenyl)-1-picrylhydrazyl) Assay

The ability of *M. oleifera* leaf extract to scavenge stable DPPH radical was measured using a spectrophotometric method (Malakarjuma and Tripathi, 2012) with slight modification. From a 1mg/ml stock solution of extract and standard (ascorbic acid), serial dilution was prepared in methanol with concentrations (200, 400, 600, 800, 1000 µg/mL). 0.2 mL of 0.1 mM DPPH in methanol solution was added to each concentration and allowed to react in the dark at room temperature for 30 min. Absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 517 nm. In this assay, 0.2 mL of 0.1 mM DPPH in methanol solution served as a blank control, and all extracts and standards were examined in triplicate. The DPPH scavenging effect (%) was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Scavenging Effect (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Control absorbance} - \text{Test absorbance})}{\text{Control absorbance}} \times 100$$

Ascorbic acid was used as a standard reference compound (positive controls) for comparison. The IC₅₀ values of the extract and standard were determined by plotting DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity (%) vs. Concentration. IC₅₀ value represented the concentration of the compounds that caused 50 % inhibition of DPPH radical formation.

Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP Assay)

FRAP assay was conducted according to the method [5]. FRAP assay depends upon the reduction of ferric tripyridyl triazine {Fe (III)-TPTZ} complex to ferrous tripyridyl triazine {Fe (II)-TPTZ}. Ferrous has an intense blue colour, which can be monitored at 593 nm.

Briefly, working solution of the FRAP reagent was prepared immediately by mixing 10 mL of acetate buffer (pH 3.6) with 1 ml of ferric chloride hexahydrate (20 mM in distilled water) and 1 ml of 2,4,6-tris(2-pyridyl)-s-triazine (TPTZ) (10 mM in 40 mM HCl). 3ml of the working solution was added to 100 µL of distilled water, Sample and Ascorbic acid in three separate test tubes. The solutions were incubated at 37 °C for 4 minutes, and the absorbance value was taken three times using a spectrophotometer at 593 nm. Distilled water served as the blank solution. A standard curve was prepared by using standard solutions of ferrous sulphate (FeSO₄). The results were expressed as mM Fe²⁺ equivalent.

Statistical Analysis

The tests were carried out in triplicate, and results were expressed as Mean ± standard deviation (SD). Statistical comparisons were performed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The data were analyzed using GraphPad Instat 3, with p - p-value less than 0.05 considered to be significantly different.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of steroids, phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, anthraquinone, and cardiac glycosides, while saponins were negative. The Methanolic Extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaf demonstrated a 6.5% yield, indicating efficient extraction of bioactive compounds. The qualitative phytochemical screening, as shown in Table 1, revealed that Methanolic *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract contained various components such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, anthraquinone, cardiac glycosides, tannins, and steroids, with the absence of saponins, which is comparable to the work of Malakarjuna and Tripathi (2012). The quantitative phytochemical result shown in Table 4 showed the total content of Phenols, Flavonoids, Tannins, and Alkaloids as 177.5±3.37 expressed in mg GAE/g of extract, 49.5±8.99 expressed in mg QE/g of extract, 65.3±5.45 expressed in mg GAE/g of extract, and 81.5±3.84 expressed in mg AE/g of extract, respectively. Phenolic compounds are known as powerful antioxidants due to their ability to scavenge free radicals and superoxide radicals (Sembiring *et al.*, 2018). The radical scavenging activity is attributed to hydroxyl groups replacing the aromatic ring of the phenolic components. Polyphenols have been reported

to possess anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, and anti-microbial properties. Flavonoids also have anticancer activities and have the property of preventing oxidative cell damage (Alseekh *et al.*, 2020). These results showed the rich composition of phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, and alkaloids, which are known

for their antioxidant and health-promoting properties. The high phenolic and flavonoid contents correlate with the observed antioxidant activity, as they are known to neutralize free radicals and prevent oxidative damage.

Table 1: Total Phytochemical Content in Methanolic Extract of *Moringa oleifera* Leaf.

S/N	Phytochemical	Total Content
1	Total Phenolic Content (mg GAE/g of extract)	177.5± 3.37 ^a
2	Total Flavonoid Content (mg QE/g of extract)	49.5 ±8.99 ^b
3	Total Tannin Content (mg GAE/g of extract)	65.3± 5.45 ^c
4	Total Alkaloid Content (mg AE/g of extract)	81.5± 3.84 ^d

Values are expressed as means ± SD of a triplicate sample (n = 3). Values having different superscript letters down the column are statistically different ($p \leq 0.05$).

The Antioxidant activities of *M. oleifera* extract were determined using the DPPH and FRAP assays. Antioxidants act by donating an electron to unstable free radicals to neutralize them and reduce their potential for harm (Gulcin, 2020). The DPPH assay showed that the extract exhibited moderate free radical scavenging activity, reaching a maximum inhibition of 66.2±2.32% at 1000 µg/ml. While this is lower than that of ascorbic acid, a strong standard antioxidant having 81.9±0.1% at the same concentration, this demonstrates the extract's potential as a natural antioxidant. Overall, the result showed a concentration-dependent increase in inhibition. The % scavenging activity of DPPH was plotted against the concentration, and the IC₅₀ value (the extract concentration that scavenges 50% of the radicals) was calculated via linear regression from the graph as described by Chatterjee *et al.* (2012). The IC₅₀ values of *M. oleifera* and ascorbic acid were obtained as 820µg/ml and 361.1µg/ml, respectively. IC₅₀ value of an antioxidant is the concentration of the antioxidant required to give 50% inhibition of the probe in an

antioxidant assay, 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl in the DPPH assay. Low IC₅₀ values denote high antioxidant capacity (Fitriana *et al.*, 2016). According to Anteneh *et al.* (2020), transition metals have played a crucial role in generating oxygen free radicals in living organisms. These transition elements, such as iron and copper, can induce free radical generation due to unpaired electrons on their valence shells, which makes them structurally unstable. The unstable nature of these metals often directs the conversion of H₂O₂ to OH in the Fenton reaction (Hrelia and Angeloni, 2020). Antioxidants also exhibit their activity by Transition Metal Chelation (Skrovankova *et al.*, 2015). The FRAP assay result was expressed in mM Fe²⁺ equivalent as shown in Figure 1. The methanol extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaf showed an antioxidant activity of 2.71±0.01, while ascorbic acid, a known standard antioxidant exhibited a slightly higher antioxidant activity of 2.77±0.01, there is no statistical difference between the two samples ($p \geq 0.05$), which suggests that the extract has a comparable antioxidant capacity to ascorbic acid.

Table 2: Percentage (%) Inhibition of DPPH Free Radicals

S/N	Concentration	Percentage Inhibition (%)	Percentage Inhibition Acid (%)
1	200	11.5±0.72 ^a	60.0±20.18 ^b
2	400	13.0±2.41 ^c	63.4±10.83 ^d
3	600	19.9±4.23 ^e	75.3±1.76 ^f
4	800	50.7±6.12 ^g	74.5±1.45 ^h
5	1000	66.2±2.32 ⁱ	81.9±0.1 ⁱ

Values are expressed as means ± SD of a triplicate sample (n = 3). Values having different superscript letters across the row and down the column are statistically different ($p \leq 0.05$).

IC₅₀ values of *M. oleifera* and Ascorbic acid were obtained as 820µg/ml and 361.1µg/ml respectively.

Figure 1: FRAP Result of Methanolic *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Extract and Ascorbic Acid Expressed in mM Fe²⁺ Equivalent.

Key: MEMO: Methanol Extract of *Moringa oleifera*; AscA: Ascorbic acid

CONCLUSION

The methanolic extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaf demonstrated significant antioxidant activity and a rich phytochemical profile, indicating that it has diverse bioactive compounds, emphasizing its potential as a natural source of antioxidants. The DPPH assay showed the extract's highest antioxidant activity at 1000 µg/ml (66.2 ± 2.32%). However, lower than ascorbic acid activity (81.9 ± 0.1%), it is still notable, suggesting the extract has moderate potential in scavenging free radicals. FRAP assay revealed comparable antioxidant activity between *Moringa oleifera* (2.71 ± 0.01 mM Fe²⁺ equivalents) and ascorbic acid (2.77 ± 0.01 mM Fe²⁺ equivalents), with no statistically significant difference (p ≥ 0.05). The findings suggest that *Moringa oleifera* could be utilized in developing nutraceuticals and functional foods for managing oxidative stress-related conditions.

RECOMMENDATION

Further studies on the characterization of *Moringa oleifera* should be carried out to identify the bioactive compounds with free radical scavenging activity.

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